

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

CHRONOTHERAPEUTICS: CIRCADIAN RHYTHM BASED THERAPY

R.Santosh Kumar, Mangesh Pradeep Kulkarni

GITAM Institute of Pharmacy, GITAM University, Rushikonda, Visakhapatnam-45.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 22/12/2017

Available online

31/01/2018

Keywords

Circadian Rhythms,
Chronotherapy,
Patented Systems.

ABSTRACT

The functions of human body vary considerably in a day. These are due to the circadian clock of human body and can also be stated as the circadian rhythms. Depending on the variations in the circadian clock the disease patterns and its effect on the body also varies in a day. Now Chronotherapy is a new concept in the Novel Drug Delivery System [NDDS]. Chronotherapy is nothing but the treatment of many disorders or ailments like asthma, cardio-vascular disorders, hypertension, arthritis etc., by relating the drug pharmacokinetics with the changes in the biological rhythms of the human body. This principle can be achieved by the timely release of the active substance into the systemic circulation when the therapeutic effects can be maximized. The various approaches for this also have been discussed below. In this review, the concepts of biological rhythms and chronotherapy have been discussed. The very purpose of chronotherapy is to increase the efficiency of the drug molecule against the disorder and reduce the side-effects of the therapy.

Corresponding author

R. Santosh Kumar

GITAM Institute of Pharmacy,
GITAM University, Rushikonda, Visakhapatnam-45.
drsantoshrada@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **R. Santosh Kumar et al. Chronotherapeutics: Circadian Rhythm Based Therapy. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2018:8(01).**

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Biological clock is responsible for the periodic fluctuations in an organism corresponding to the periodic environmental changes. A rhythm with a 24-hour cycle is called a circadian. It is the repeating cycles of activity which occur in living organisms. It is regulated by the suprachiasmatic nucleus. It is also called as the sleep-activity cycle and is effected by the genetic makeup hence varies among the individuals.

Biological rhythms can be termed as oscillations and also be classified into three,

Circadian Rhythms-

It is the oscillations of body that are completed in 24 hours or has a 24-hour cycle.

Ultradian Rhythms-

These can be stated as the oscillation that are completed in less than 24 hours.

Infradian Rhythms-

If the oscillations take more than 24 hours they can be termed as the Infradian Rhythms. [1, 2]

For instance in the human body most of the hormonal secretions occur early in the morning or during sleep and ensure their maximum productivity. Similarly other physiological parameters like the blood pressure is also up generally during the morning hours. Coming to the disorders like rheumatoid arthritis, which is comparatively more painful in the morning while the pain decreases as the day passes, but people having osteoarthritis tend to have more pain during nights when compared to the mornings.

Figure-1: Human Biological clock.

Hence studying these biological rhythms of the human body the best time at which the maximum efficacy of a drug molecule can be calculated and worked upon.

This chronobiology (biology that examines periodic phenomena in living organisms and their adaptation to solar- and lunar-related rhythms) can be carefully studied, examined for the development of a novel drug delivery system called the Chronotherapy.

Chronotherapy

Chronotherapy or Chronotherapeutics can be defined as the treatment of an ailment, disease or a disorder depending or in association with the biological rhythms of the body to maximize the therapeutic effect and minimize the side effect of the therapeutic ingredient. The efficiency as well as the toxicity of the drug also depends on the rhythmic differences of the human body. In the modern era of medicine chronotherapy has been one of the most juvenile concepts of drug delivery system. The first chronotherapeutic delivery system was developed in the early 1960s and has been under development.

Generally in case of a conventional method of drug delivery i.e. the oral route of administration the drug molecule tends to pass the first pass metabolism and later enters the blood stream. Here the drug from the dosage form is released constantly for the certain period of time. If this method has to be coordinated with the biological rhythms it becomes a tedious process for the patient and the compliance rate is reduced as the dosage form has to be administered in several units. To overcome this problem a novel drug delivery system comprising the mechanisms like pulsatile release of the drugs with the help of multiple coated films, pH sensitive mechanisms etc. could help us attain this property. By developing such dosage forms the degradation of the drug molecule in the upper part of the gastro intestinal tract can also be surpassed and a specific site of action can also be achieved. It has been evident that many dosage forms have been proven more efficacious when administered according the sleep-activity module. [3-6]

Disorders that can be treated:

There are not many pathological conditions having the application of chronotherapy for their effective treatment. A few of them are listed below:

- Cardiac Disorders.
- Arthritis.
- Hypercholesterolemia.
- Asthma.
- Diabetes.
- Ulcer.
- Epilepsy.
- Cancers.
- Pain.

Brief description of the above pathological conditions:**Cardiac disorders:**

Cardio-Vascular system of the human body is one of the most sophisticated systems and also shows its adherence towards the circadian clock. Also it was one the physiological function that was first discovered to have irregularity with the difference in the human activity cycle in other words the sleep-activity cycle. Various parameters of the cardio-vascular system like the [i] Heart Rate [ii] Blood Pressure [iii] Vasoconstriction [iv] Vasodilation generally show the variations time to time.

Majorly the cases of cardiac arrest are reported early in the morning, and a reason for this could be the increased blood pressure. This is found to occur because of the increased levels of epinephrine and norepinephrine which is released at night or during the rest phase. It was found that the calcium channel blocker administered during the bedtime may help to reduce the risk. Although the effect of oral nitrates, β -adreno receptor blockers and the calcium channel blockers are rhythmically dependent. Thus, the chronotherapy can be applied for the prevention of cardiac disorders like angina and hypertension. [7-10]

For example, in case of hypertension the pulsatile delivery module can be employed for the release of the therapeutic ingredient when the blood pressure is high. This could be helpful in preventing cardiac arrest.

Arthritis:

Rheumatoid Arthritis and Osteo Arthritis also show a major variation in their activity. Both of them show relation with the biological cycle, Rheumatoid Arthritis patients experience severe pain in the early morning and the patients suffering from Osteo Arthritis has pain generally during the nights. Thus by employing the applications of chronotherapy i.e. sustained release dosage forms the active drug can be made to release and show its therapeutic action when the pain is at the peak stages. [11,12]

Asthma:

As the above disorders even asthma has a particular biological pattern of occurrence. It is observed that the symptoms of asthma aggravate during the late night hours than the morning up to 100 times than normal. This phenomenon takes place due to the variance in many physiological secretions and responses during the day and night. For Example, the levels of cortisol in our body during the night are low, whose function is anti-inflammatory. Followed by Histamine that is responsible for bronchoconstriction is also high during the night. And the combined effects of these two agents results in asthmatic symptoms. The degree of bronchoconstriction is the highest around 4:00 AM. Thus, the administration of Anti-Asthmatic drugs at night is more appreciable for efficient activity. [13]

Diabetes:

In case of juvenile diabetes, circadian rhythms of insulin requirement and action are of clinical importance. This happens when the immune system of the body destroys the beta cells of pancreas which are responsible for the production of insulin. Generally, insulin is released in pulsatile fashion but sometimes it is action. This kind of action proves helpful in continuous supply of insulin. The efficient action may be effected by stress hormones, cortisol, epinephrine and growth hormone. Partly intrinsic rhythmicity, dehydration and prolonged insulin withdrawal may induce a secondary feed-back signal on insulin release which can help to raise blood glucose levels. The modulators of insulin release and action are secreted in a circadian fashion and also impress the mode of release. Providing basal insulin exogenously to patients with diabetes inhibits hepatic glucose production. [14-16]

Hypercholesterolemia:

Hypercholesterolemia is nothing but the presence of high cholesterol content in the blood. In this the relation that exists with the biological rhythm is, generally cholesterol synthesis occurs predominantly during the night. This is done by the HMG-CoA cycle. If the drug is administered during the night rather than the mornings the effectiveness of the therapeutic ingredient would be greater. This could also be helpful for lowering the side effects by preventing the administration of the drug when not required. [17, 18]

Figure-2: Schematic representation of diseases showing circadian rhythmicity.

Ulcer:

Ulcers are the lesions that occur in the gastric mucosa because of the local area tissue damage due to excess acid secretion or action over the walls of the stomach. A circadian pattern of release in the gastric acid can be observed, where the amount of gastric secretion is highest in the evenings and night when compared to the mornings. In the gastric secretion a prominent rhythm of six months was found which was stable and the days where the gastric or duodenal perforations were more prominent were Thursday-Friday and Sunday-Monday.

Hence the suppression of the nocturnal acid secretion was of more importance for the healing of a gastric or duodenal ulcer. A dosage regimen of H₂ Antagonists at the night proves to be helpful.[19,20]

Epilepsy:

The seizures that occur in case of epilepsy also exhibit a circadian rhythmic pattern and their prominence also sometimes depends on the biological cycle of the humans although it varies from patient to patient. The behavioral chronobiology provides the detection of new regulation processes that concerns central mechanisms of epilepsy because the circadian psycho physiological patterns of epilepsy show dynamic biological systems which show some inter-modulating endogenous processes between observation and seizure susceptibility.

Such chronotherapeutic development of dosage forms with respect to the chronobiology may help in the invention of new aspects and also the betterment of the ailment. [21, 22]

Cancers:

In the case of Cancer chemotherapy may be more effective and less toxic if cancer drugs are administered at carefully selected times that take advantage of tumor cell cycles while less toxic to normal tissue. The rhythmic changes in tumor blood flow and cancer growth are relevant both when tumors are small and growing most rapidly and when they are larger and growing more slowly. The blood flow to tumors and tumor growth rate are each up to threefold greater during each daily activity phase of the circadian cycle than during the daily rest phase.

Normal bone marrow DNA synthesis peaks around noon, DNA synthesis in malignant lymphoma cells peaks near midnight. By treatment at midnight, more tumor cell could be killed with same dose of S-phase active cytotoxic therapy and with relatively little bone marrow damage, and the amount of tissue damage caused can be minimized with a very few side effects of chemotherapy.[24-25]

Pain:

Pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage. It is generally the very first symptom for most of the ailments. It also follows a rhythmic pattern but it is not the same in all the tissues of the body. For example the sensitivity threshold of the gingiva to a cold stimulus was maximal at 18:00 and reached a peak at 03:00 hours. Tooth sensitivity was observed to be lowest between 15:00 and 18:00 hours, with a peak in pain intensity at 08:00 hrs. The non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents (NSAIDs) may be more effective at relieving pain, if the drug is administered at least 4 to 6 hours before the pain reaches its peak. Thus, effective scheduling of the drug has to be done to maximize the therapeutic effect and minimize the adverse or side effect. [25-28]

The above are few of the pathological conditions that are affected by the circadian rhythms for their advancement and also the accurate schedule of the dosage regimen to get the best therapeutic outcome. There are few other neurologically related diseases like the Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease which also could be treated based on their circadian pattern.

Table-1: Examples of drugs for the respective pathological conditions.

DRUGS	EXAMPLES
Cardiovascular drugs	Verapamil, Propranolol, Diltiazem
Arthritis	NSAIDs, Glucocorticoids
Anti-Cholesterolemic Agents	Lovastatin, Simvastatin
Anti-Asthmatic drugs	Theophylline, Terbutaline
Anti-Diabetics	Sulfonylureas Insulin, pioglitazone
Anti-Ulcer agents	Theophylline, Albuterol, Terbutaline
Anti-Cancer drugs	Cisplatin, Doxorubicin, Methothrexate
NSAID's	Ketoprofen, Indomethacin

Chronotherapeutic Systems

Chronotherapeutic systems is nothing but the methodology that is applied for the development of a dosage form which can meet all the characteristics of releasing the drug as expected match its therapeutic outcomes synchronizing the biological rhythms.

Ideal characteristics:

- It should be easy to administer thus increasing the patient compliance.
- It should have the capacity to release the therapeutic ingredient when desired i.e. according to the circadian rhythm.
- It should have the desired Bio-Availability.
- It should be Biodegradable.
- They should be non-toxic, non-irritant.
- They should have a specific triggering biomarker of disease state in order to reduce the side effects.
- In case of injectable it should be isotonic to the body fluids and should be biocompatible.
- The manufacturing should be economic.

To ensure the above ideal characteristics of a chronotherapeutic dosage form the active therapeutic ingredient has to be correctly and efficiently turned into a desired type of dosage form by using the various established, modern and patented techniques of the pharmaceutical industry at a reasonable and economic production values.

Need for chronotherapy

First pass metabolism:

Some drugs like salicylamide undergoes extensive first pass metabolism and loses its potency. Thus chronotherapeutic systems can help to overcome this problem.

Local therapeutic need:

To prevent the loss of the drug through intestinal absorption by local administration of the drug. For example, in case of a Bowel Inflammation.

Special Chronopharmacological needs:

To match the circadian rhythmicity of the human body, this proves efficient for the treatment and also minimizes the side effects.

Gastric irritation or drug instability in gastric fluid:

For drugs that are chemically instable and cause irritation to the gastro-intestinal tract.

Sustained Release:

This is one of the major needs of chronotherapeutics where there is a continuous release of drug in the plasma, giving a good therapeutic effect. [29-34]

Advantages of Chronotherapy:

- Improved patient compliance.
- Design Flexibility.
- Reduced risk of mucosal irritation.
- Sustained release of drug.
- Avoids undesired side effects.

Disadvantages of Chronotherapy:

- Higher production cost.
- Low manufacturing efficiency.
- Low drug loading capacity.
- Incomplete release of drug etc.

The mechanisms that can be used are classified and explained in brief below.

Time Dependent Release Chronotherapeutic Systems

These systems can also be called as the stimuli dependent.

- Capsular systems.
- Layered systems.
- Reservoir systems with rupturable polymer coating.
- Soluble or Eroding polymer coating Reservoir systems.
- Floating systems or Low density.

Pulsatile Drug Delivery Systems

Pulsatile delivery systems demand release of drug after a lag time as a rapid and transient release of certain amount of molecules within a short time period immediately after a predetermined off- release period.

- Temperature sensitive pulsed- release delivery systems.
- Enzyme dependent pulsatile-release systems.
- Glucose concentration dependent insulin release systems.
- pH sensitive pulsatile drug delivery systems.
- Biodegradable polymers coating.

Patented Systems for Manufacture Of Chronotherapeutics

This class comprises of the few established methods of manufacture of the chronotherapeutic dosage systems.

- OROS® technology.
- CODAS® technology.
- TIMERx® technology.
- CEFORM® technology.
- DIFFUCAPS® technology.
- PORT® technology.
- EGALET® technology.
- GEOMATRIX® technology.
- PULSINCAP® technology.
- PULSYSTM® technology.

Time Dependent Release Chronotherapeutic Systems:

Capsular Systems:

Capsular systems are mainly consists of an insoluble capsule body and degradable plugs made of substances that can swell. The lag time is controlled by plug, which is pushed away by swelling or dissolution and drug is released from the insoluble capsule. This method can also be called as the “Pulsincap”. The outer shell is made up of swellable materials like hydrogel which seals the drug contents into the capsule body. Once they come in contact of dissolution medium, the hydrogel swells and after a lag time, the plug pushes itself outside the capsule and rapidly releases the drug. Hydrophilic polymers are generally used for plugs like hydroxypropylcellulose, polyvinyl-acetate, and polyethylene-oxide etc. For water-insoluble drugs, a rapid release can be ensured by inclusion of effervescent agents or disintegrants. [35, 36].

Figure-3: Mechanism of capsular systems.

Layered systems:

Layered systems as in the name have multiple layers of coating over the dosage form which ultimately helps in timed release of the drug. They have one or two impermeable or semipermeable polymeric coatings of films or compressed layers applied on both sides of the core. The drug can be made available as two layers in the core. An intermediate layer, made of swellable polymers, separates the drug layers. As the two polymeric layer dissolve the drug molecules disintegrate and the active ingredient is released. The material used for coating and its thickness can help in controlling the time of release, giving a pulsatile release i.e. sustained release of the API. [36].

Figure-4: Descriptive representation of layered systems.

Reservoir systems with rupturable coat:

The mechanism of reservoir systems with rupturable coat is very simple and also similar to that of the layered systems. In this the active constituent is taken as the core of the dosage form, surrounding the core a layer which is hydrophilic or swells when comes in contact with the solvent is coated. This layer absorbs the solvent and hence there is a pressure buildup inside the tablet. The outer core can hold the pressure up to some extent and then bursts open to release the core or the active ingredient that is embedded in the core of the tablet. Here the tablet involves three layers, first is the core, second one is the swellable layer and the third is the rupturable coat. The swellable layer helps in growing the size of the tablet and thus a pressure buildup is seen inside the tablet. This can be achieved when the drug is required to show its action when the pH is around 5-6. [37].

Figure-5: Reservoir systems with rupturable coat.

Soluble or Erodible polymer coated reservoir systems:

In this type of pulsatile drug delivery agents the release of the drug is controlled by the presence of a polymer which gets solubilized or gets eroded when conditions comes in contact with a desired solvent band pH. The lag between the releases of the drug can be controlled by controlling the thickness of the polymer coat.

Substances like HPMC and acrylate polymers have been observed to meet the desired action of delivering drugs to various sites in gastrointestinal tract due to their solubility /eroding properties. HPMC has been found to hold the drug for around 4 hours which is sufficient for its release in the intestinal mucosa of human body. [35-38].

Figure-6: Schematic figure of Soluble or Erodible polymer coated reservoir systems.

Floating/low density systems:

This is one of the recent approaches for the pulsatile drug delivery or the chronotherapeutic drug delivery whose basic mechanism of action is by having low density than the gastric juices which make it float above the gastric materials or the gastric secretion.

The lower bulk density of the dosage form gives buoyancy to the tablet and this helps it to remain in the stomach even after the stomach is emptied into the intestine. This approach is done in order to prevent the drug from entering into the intestinal environment. Thus, they enable prolonged input of the drug in the upper part of the Gastro-Intestinal tract.

A single unit or multi-unit systems can be developed by many mechanisms like:

- 1) Muco-adhesive systems- these systems involves use of bio-adhesive polymers which adhere to the mucosal epithelia of the stomach,
- 2) Raft forming systems- produces a layer on top of gastric fluids,
- 3) Effervescent systems- these systems release gases like carbon dioxide to stay buoyant in the stomach. [39]

Figure-7: Figure explaining the mechanism of floating/low density systems.

Pulsatile Drug Delivery Systems

Temperature sensitive pulsed release systems:

The body tissues vary in their temperatures and are not same. This phenomenon can be utilized to gain a pulsatile dosage form, i.e. for example, in case of cancer the mutated cells generally have greater temperature than that of the normal cells. [41]

It becomes easier to target such cells and get a therapeutic action at the preferred site and at the required time. A few hydrogels that are thermo-responsive can be incorporated into the dosage form which further at the desired temperature swell and burst open to release the drug.

Enzyme dependent pulsatile release systems:

This is another method of gaining a lagged drug release where the releasing of the drug depends on the presence of enzymes in the particular area of release. This method generally finds its application in the treatment of colonic diseases. [42-44]

The flora present in colon releases some enzymes which triggers the release of drug molecules from the specifically developed dosage form. The choice of excipients are polysaccharides like pectin, guar gum etc.

Glucose concentration dependent Insulin release systems:

In case of diabetes mellitus there is subsequent increase in the glucose concentration in the blood. A dosage form that gets activated in the presence of high glucose levels can be developed using a stimuli sensitive hydrogel which contains glucose-oxygenase enzyme which proves helpful in converting the glucose to gluconic acid. As an acid is formed there takes a pH change in the system which helps in the sudden release of Insulin, which ultimately lowers the blood glucose levels. [41-45]

pH sensitive pulsatile drug delivery systems:

In the pH sensitive dosage forms the polymer which is sensitive to a particular pH are applied as an outer coat of the dosage form. As the polymer is pH sensitive, when the zone of required pH is arrived the capsule or the tablet bursts open immediately to release the active ingredient. Generally polymers like carboxy methyl cellulose, various grades of Eudragit and phallates are used. pH sensitive pulsatile drug delivery systems are most widely accepted ones and they are in turn used as one of the mechanisms in developing the sophisticated dosage forms. Akhgari et.al studied on the optimum ratio of eudragit1100 and Eudragit S1000 for colonic delivery of indomethacin pellets for chronotherapy of rheumatoid arthritis etc. [46, 47]

Bio-degradable polymer coating systems:

The mechanism behind this novel delivery system is that the polymer that is used for the preparation of the dosage form degrades with the biological activity of some microorganisms etc. They generally find their application in the treatment of colonic diseases as the polymeric coating of the dosage form there is degrade by the bacteria present there. [42-48]

Patented systems for the manufacture of chronotherapeutics

Working the various methods of pulsatile drug delivery systems many sophisticated methods that could meet the requirements to treat the disorder in the required pattern and possibly give the least side effects. They are briefly discussed in the table below. [39-51]

Table-2: Patented techniques of chronotherapy.

SR.No	TECHNOLOGY	MECHANISM USED IN THE TECHNOLOGY
1	OROS®	It is an osmotic pump system comprising of a central drug reservoir surrounded by a semi-permeable membrane, and then by osmotically active agents with a laser-drilled orifice. Ex: Methylphenidate HCl, an Anti-Psychotic drug.
2	GEOMATRIX®	The controlled release is achieved by constructing a multilayered tablet made of two basic key components; 1) hydrophilic polymers such as HPMC and 2) surface controlling barrier layers. Active loaded core surface that is available for drug release when exposed to the fluid is controlled by barrier layers.
3	CODAS®	Chronotherapeutic oral drug absorption system consisting of drug loaded beads that are coated with release-controlling polymer. Polymer consists of water-soluble and water-insoluble polymers to induce a lag time. Ex: Verapamil HCl, for hypertension.
4	TIMERx®	A novel polysaccharide system that uses xanthan gum and locust bean gum in the presence of secondary and tertiary components, to form water-soluble granules, which facilitates the drug release. Ex: An oral, CR opioid analgesic oxymorphone.
5	CEFORM®	Biodegradable polymers are subjected to varying temperature, and flow processes to produce microspheres of uniform size and shape rendering the required action. Ex: Diltiazem HCl, for the management of hypertension.
6	DIFFUCAPS®	It is a Multiparticulate system consisting of a core, coated with an active pharmaceutical ingredient mixed with a water-soluble composition. This may be in the form of beads, pellets, granules. Ex: Propranolol HCl, for treating hypertension.
7	PORT®	It consists of a gelatin capsule coated with a semi permeable membrane and an insoluble plug and an osmotically active agent along with the drug. When the capsule comes in contact with the dissolution medium, water diffuses across the membrane, resulting in increased pressure inside that ejects the plug
8	EGALET®	It consists of an impermeable shell with two lag plugs; active drug is sandwiched between the plugs. After the inert plugs have eroded, the drug is released.
9	PULSINCAP®	It consists of a drug reservoir coupled within a water-soluble capsule body. The open end of capsule is plugged with swellable polymers that swells and pushes itself out when in contact with fluid and releases the drug.
10	PULSYSTM®	A pulsatile release system that consists of one immediate-release and two delayed-release components with the use of soluble and insoluble coatings on top of the active ingredient.
11	CHRONOTOPIC®	It is basically drug containing core coated with an outer release controlling layer.
12	IPDAS®	It disintegrates and disperses beads containing a drug in the stomach, which subsequently passes into the duodenum and along the GIT in a controlled manner. The release is controlled by the polymer system used to coat the beads.

Current Status & Future Challenges of Chronotherapy:

Chronotherapy is one of the most modern methods of treatment of various human diseases by synchronizing the therapeutic activity of the drugs with the human biological clock to reduce the side effects and increase the efficiency of the dosage form. It proves very helpful for the patients as the major route of administration is by Oral cavity and is very compliant.

As it is a new approach there are only few ailments treated officially by chronotherapy. It is still under research to overcome the drawbacks like cost effectiveness, operational ease etc. Their performance in vivo has often not been tested, and clinical results are lacking and will have to be closely examined before they may be rendered applicable for clinical use. Future research of rhythmically synced chronotherapeutics is on the demand now and this would prove helpful for the developing not only tablets but also few vaccines etc.

CONCLUSION

Chronotherapy can be called the need of the hour as such method of managing an ailment with possibly the least side effects is of urge in the field of medicine. A plenty of research and experimentation is under the process for the development of pulsatile release dosage forms. The sustained actin of these drugs is of demand and has a very high compliance. It is one approach to increasing the efficiency of pharmacotherapy is administering drugs at times during which they are best tolerated. The monitoring of rhythm, overcome of rhythm disruption and manipulation of rhythm are essential to improved progress and are promised by the pulsatile drug delivery agents. Chronotherapeutics having greater impact on the treatment and recovery overcomes many drug delivery problems while also increasing the acceptance rate are of high demand.

REFERENCES

1. Reinberg A, Smolensky MH, Biologic rhythms and medicine. cellular, metabolic, pathophysiological, and pharmacologic aspects. Springer, Heidelberg Springer-Verlag, Heidelberg, 1983, 305.
2. Smolensky, M.D.; D'Alonzo, G.E. Biologic rhythms and medicine. *Am. J. Med.*, 1988, 85, 34-46.
3. Lemmer B, Labrecque G. Chronopharmacology and chronotherapeutics: definitions and concepts. *Chronobiol Int.* 1987;4(3):319–29.
4. Evans RM, Marain C. Taking Your Medication: A Question of Timing. American Medical Association: 1996:3-8.
5. R. Santosh Kumar et al. An Update on Chronotherapeutic Drug Delivery Systems. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.* 2015;5(09).
6. Lemmer B., From the Biological Clock to Chronopharmacology, *Medpharm Publ.* Stuttgart 1996; 91-117.
7. Lamberg L. Chronotherapeutics: implications for drug therapy. *American Pharmacy* 1991; NS31(11): 20-23.
8. Blaustein MP., Sodium Ions, Calcium Ions, Blood Pressure Regulation, and Hypertension: A Reassessment and A Hypothesis, *Am J Physiol Cell Physiol* 1977; 232 :165–173
9. Verdecchia P., Porcellati C., Schillaci G., Ambulatory Blood Pressure: An Independent Predictor of Prognosis in Essential Hypertension, *Hypertension* 1994; 24:793–801.
10. Mancia G., Autonomic Modulation of the Cardiovascular System during Sleep, *N Engl J Med* 1993; 328 : 347- 349.
11. Kumar Amit & Ranga Sonam. Pulsatile Drug Delivery System: Method and Technology Review. *Int. J. Drug Dev. & Res.* 2012; 4(4):95-107.
12. Jha N, Bapat S: Chronobiology and chronotherapeutics. *Kathmandu University Med. Jour.* 2004; 2(8):384-388.
13. Smolensky MH, Lemmer B, Reinberg AE (2007) Chronobiology and chronotherapy of allergic rhinitis and bronchial asthma. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* 59: 852-882.
14. Halsas M, Hietala J, Veski P, Jürjenson H, Marvola M. Morning vs. evening dosing of ibuprofen using conventional and time-controlled release formulations. *Int J Pharm* 1999; 189: 179-185.
15. Anwar YA, White WB. Chronotherapeutics for cardiovascular disease. *Drugs* 1998; 55: 631- 643.
16. Reinberg AE. Concepts of circadian chronopharmacology. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 1991;618:102-15
17. Patel JD, Aneja K, Majumdar S H, “Pulsatile Drug Delivery System: A "User Friendly" Dosage Form” *JPRHC* 2010; 2: 204-215.
18. Svanes C., Sothorn RB., Sorbye H., Rhythmic Patterns in Incidence of Peptic Ulcer Perforation over 5.5 Decades in Norway, *Chronobiol. Int* 1998; 15: 241-264.
19. Saitoh T., Watanabe Y., Kubo Y., Shinagawa M., Otsuka K., Ohkawa SA., Watanabe T., Intra-gastric Acidity and Circadian Rhythm, *Biomed Pharmacother* 2000; 55: 138-141.
20. Sharma G S, Srikanth MV, Uhumwangho MU, Phani Kumar K S et al, “Recent Trends in Pulsatile Drug Delivery Systems”, *Int. J .Pharm.* 2010;2:201-208.
21. Frishman WH., Glasser S., Stone P., Deedwania PC., Johnson M., Fakouhi TD., Comparison of Controlled-Onset, Extended-Release Verapamil with Amlodipine and Amlodipine Plus Atenolol on Exercise Performance and Ambulatory Ischemia in Patients with Chronic Stable Angina Pectoris, *Am J Cardiol* 1999; 83: 507–514.
22. Sangalli M.E., Maroni A., Zema L., Busetti C., Giordano F., Gazzaniga A. In vitro and in vivo evaluation of an oral system for time and /or site specific drug delivery. *J. Contr. Rel.* 2001; 73: 103-110.
23. Gandhi BR, Mundada AS, Gandhi PP. Chronopharmaceutics: as a clinically relevant drug delivery system. *Drug delivery*, 18(1), 2011, 1-18.
24. Sarasija S and Pathak S: Chronotherapeutics: emerging role of biorhythms in optimizing Drug therapy. *Indian J Pharm Sci*, 67(2), 2005, 135-40.
25. Marikki H. Development and biopharmaceutical evaluation of press coated tablet taking account of circadian rhythms of disease. Academic dissertation.
26. Clench J., Reinberg A., Dziewanowska Z., Ghata, Smolensky M., Circadian Changes in the Bioavailability and Effects of Indomethacin in Healthy Subjects, *Eur J Clin Pharmacol* 1981; 20: 359-369.
27. Ollagnier M., Decousus H., Cherrah Y., Levi F., Mechkouri M., Queneau P., Reinberg A., Circadian Changes in the Pharmacokinetics of Oral Ketoprofen, *Clin Pharmacokin* 1987; 12: 367-378.
28. Bodmeier R, Bussemer T, Dashevsky A. A pulsatile drug delivery system based on rupturable coated hard gelatin capsules. *J. cont. Rel.* 2003;93:331-339.
29. Maroni A, Sangalli ME, Cerea M, Busetti C, Giordano F, Gazzaniga A. Low viscosity HPMC coating of soft and hard gelatin capsules for delayed and colonic release: preliminary investigations on process parameters and in *vitro* release performances. *Proceed Int. Control Rel. Bioact. Mater.* 1999; 26: 887-888.
30. Ueda.S., Yamaguchi.H., Kotani.M., Kimura.S, Tokunaga.Y, Kagayama.A, Hata.T, Development of a novel drug release system, time – controlled explosion system (TES): III. Relation between lag time and membrane thickness, *Chemical Pharma Bulletin* 1994; 42: 364–367.
31. Badve.SS., Sher.P., Korde.A., Pawar.AP., Development of hollow/ porous calcium pectinate beads for floating–pulsatile drug delivery, *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics* 2007; 65: 85–93.
32. Sawada.T., Kondo.H., Nakashima.H., Sako.K., Hayashi.M., Time-release compression-coated core tablet containing nifedipine for chronopharmaco-therapy, *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 2004; 280: 103-111.

33. Ueda.S., Yamaguchi.H., Kotani.M., Kimura.S., Tokunaga.Y., Kagayama.A., Hata.T., Development of a novel drug release system, time – controlled explosion system (TES): II. Design of multiparticulate TES and in – vitro drug release properties, Chemical Pharma Bulletin 1994; 42: 359–363.
34. Bhargavi RA (2012) Comprehensive Review of Pulsatile Drugs. International Research Journal of Pharmacy 3: 106-108.
35. Krogel.I., Bodmeier.R., Pulsatile drug release from an insoluble capsule body controlled by an erodible plug, Pharmaceutical Research 1998;15: 474-48.
36. Sica D., Frishman WH., Manowitz N., Pharmacokinetics of Propranolol After Single and Multiple Dosing with Sustained Released Propranolol or Propranolol CR (Innopran XL™), A New Chronotherapeutic Formulation, Heart Dis 2003; 5: 176.
37. Gajanan NP, Monica R, Sameer B, Anuradha R (2009) Design, Evaluation and Comparative Study of Pulsatile Release from Tablet and Capsule Dosage Forms. Iranian J Pharma Sci Summer 5: 119-128.
38. Efentakis M, Koligliati S, Vlachou M. Design and evaluation of a dry coated drug delivery system with an impermeable cup, swellable top layer and pulsatile release. Int. J Pharm. 2006; 311:147–156.
39. Somani VG., Shahi SR., Udavant YK ., Atram SC., Satpute R., Shinde NM., A Floating Pulsatile Drug Delivery System Based on Hollow Calcium Pectinate Beads, Asian J Pharm 2009; 3: 120-4.
40. Mastiholmath.VS., Dandagi.PM., Jain.SS., Gadad.AP., Kulkarni.AR, Time and pH dependent colon specific, pulsatile delivery of theophylline for nocturnal asthma International Journal of Pharmaceutics 2006; 328: 49-56.
41. Gohel.MC., Sumitra.MG., Modulation of active pharmaceutical material release from a novel ‘tablet in capsule system’ containing an effervescent blend, Journal of Controlled Release 2002; 79: 157–164.
42. Gupta.VK., Beckert.TE., Price.JC., A novel pH – and time – based multi – unit potential colonic drug delivery system.I. Development, International Journal of Pharmaceutics 2001; 213 : 83-91.
43. Volicer L., Harper DG., Manning BC., Goldstein R., Satlin A., Sundowning and Circadian Rhythms in Alzheimer's Disease, Am. J. Psychiatr 2001; 158: 704-711.
44. Karavas E, Georarakis E, Bikiaris D (2006) Application of PVP/HPMC miscible blends with enhanced mucoadhesive properties for adjusting drug release in predictable pulsatile chronotherapeutics. Eur J Pharm Biopharm 64: 115-126.
45. P Roy, A Shahiwala. Multiparticulate formulation approach to pulsatile drug delivery: Current perspectives. J Control Rel 2009;134(2):74-80.
46. Narisawa S, Nagata M, Danyoshi C, Yoshino H, Murata K, et al. (1994) An organic acid-induced sigmoidal release system for oral controlled-release preparations. Pharm Res 11: 111-116.
47. Therapeutic System Research Laboratory (TSRL Inc), PORT Technologies act sheet, Sep-2004.
48. Patil SS, Shahiwala A (2014) Patented pulsatile drug delivery technologies for chronotherapy. Expert Opin Ther Pat 24: 845-856.
49. Rita Lala, Nikita A. Nandgaonkar Chronotherapeutic Drug Delivery Systems. Pharma Times, 42(12), 2010, 20-22.
50. Sruthy N V., Sajeeth CI., K Santhi., Desing and Evaluation of pH Sensitive Multiparticulate System for Chronotherapeutic Delivery of Carvedilol, International Journal of comprehensive Pharmacy 2011; 5(11):1-5.
51. Mahanjan AN., Pancholi SS., Formulation and Evaluation of Timed Delayed Capsule Device for Chronotherapeutic Delivery of Terbutaline Sulphate , Ars Pharm 2010; 50 (4) : 215-223.

54878478451171232

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

